

All Patient Cases (images and clinical data) collected until 24/04/2024 in the CHAIMELEON Repository related to Rectum cancer.

ID: fa55afe4-7bb5-4531-9211-c51a4df6b2c8

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/fa55afe4-7bb5-4531-9211-c51a4df6b2c8/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 537

Subjects count: 360

Age range: Between 28 years and 89 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): RECTUM, ABDOMEN, PELVIS, PROSTATE, BLADDER, ARM, ABDOMENPELVIS, PANCREAS, CANALANAL, UTERUS, PELVISLOWEREXTR, PENIS, Unknown

Modality: MR